

Problems Facing The Teachers Of The Lower Basic Stage In The Application Of The Ramp Program According To Some Variables

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Problems , Minimum Basic Stage Parameters , Ram Program</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5192851</p>	<p><i>The aim of this study is to display the problems that faced teachers of the lower basic stage in the application of the RAM program (read with comprehension, solve with understanding). The sample of present study included (77) female teachers belong to the Giza District. The objectives of present study can be achieved via a questionnaire related to the problems of (15) items was prepared. The descriptive approach was used and the statistical analyses were done by reference to (the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program to present the results related to this study.</i></p> <p><i>The present results displayed that a degree of problems faced by the teachers came to a medium degree. Also these results presented that there were no statistically significant differences due to the variable years of experience, and the results displayed the presence of statistically significant differences for the variable number of students in favor of the category 22 or more. Through the results, the researchers recommend the importance of dealing with the problems facing the application of the RAM program.</i></p>

Introduction

The basic education stage is a critical stage on that the subsequent stages of education depend, as it is the zari stone in shaping the knowledge structure of the student. Therefore, the Ministry of Education cares and keeps pace with the programs that seek to improve and develop the knowledge of our students, and the mediator who implements and implements these programs is the teacher, who is the platform that shines The way for the promising and rising generation of tomorrow's generation through doing its work to the utmost of its energies and effort in providing them with basic skills in the education process and in developing the thinking skills of its students by keeping pace with developments in the field of education and advanced courses and programs that contribute and help in activating the education process and in raising the level of competence of students from During positive active education, despite the effort made by the teacher, she may face some problems and obstacles when using modern education programs.

The primary school teacher faces a number of problems in the teaching process, including those related to learners, their characteristics, abilities and motivation, as well as problems related to teaching methods and the courses offered to teachers, as well as one of the problems that teachers face is communicating with parents as complements to the educational process (Al-Harbi, 2015).

The study of Tim, Gabein, Saad, Hammam, and Al-Dalou (2018) indicated that there are problems facing primary school teachers, including those related to the teacher and the appropriateness of the curriculum as well as school administration and the suitability of the curriculum as well as the facilities provided to the teacher in the teaching process.

1. The Problem of Study:

The teaching profession is one of the professions that requires effort from the teacher, and since the teacher is the facilitator who facilitates the methods of learning and teaching students, it requires from the teacher personal competencies and special skills that are given to the teacher by joining the training courses, programs and initiatives provided by the Ministry. The Ministry of Education strives to improve the educational process. The Al-Ram initiative is one of the initiatives used by the Ministry of Education that seeks to train and guide public school teachers to improve learning outcomes.

The researchers noticed that there were some complaints from female teachers about the application of the Ram program, and when they hosted female teachers to talk about the program at the university, they mentioned the program's effectiveness, but they also pointed out that there are problems and difficulties they face in implementing the program.

This is what Tim and others (2018) indicated to the existence of problems facing primary school teachers, and Al-Sharari (2011) indicated that the programs and courses that the teacher enrolls in are among the problems facing the teacher.

Hamadaneh (2017) study mentioned the factors that affect the success of the application of the Ram program, and therefore any deficiency or defect in these factors constitutes a problem for the teachers in applying the Ram program and achieving the desired goal.

Hence the study questions, which are:

-What are the problems faced by the teacher of the first three grades when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic?

-Are there statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the problems facing the teacher of the first three grades when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic belong to the variable number of students?

- Are there statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the problems facing the teacher of the first three grades when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic due to the educational qualification variable?

3. The Value of Study:

The value of the study appears in that it is one of the few studies and the first study, to the knowledge of the researchers, that dealt with the issue of the problems of the parameters of the lower basic stage in the application of the RAM program.

The value of the study as follows:

1.This study helps officials in the Ministry of Education to identify the problems facing teachers and to develop proposals.This study enriches the Arab and Jordanian library because of its importance in shedding light on the problems of teachers in the application of modern education programs.

2.This study helps the teachers to find ways to deal with the problems they face in the application of educational programs.

3.Helps urge researchers to conduct new research by reviewing the findings and recommendations.

4. The Limits of Study:

Human limits: all teachers of lower basic stage in public schools which perform the Ramp system.

Spatial boundaries: Directorate of Education - Central Badia

Time limits: 2018-2019

5. Terminology of Study:

Problems: They are the physical or moral difficulties and obstacles that limit and prevent the achievement of the desired educational and educational goals and cause fatigue and frustration for teachers (Shehadeh, 2012).

-The teachers of lower basic stage: they are teachers who teach the stage which contains classes from the first to the third grade.

The Reading and Arithmetic Initiative (RAMP): an initiative that aims to improve the development and development of reading comprehension and arithmetic with understanding. It is an initiative used by the Jordanian Ministry of Education.

6. Theoretical framework:

The teaching profession is considered one of the professions that has its own character. It requires the teacher special effort, endurance, development and keeping pace with everything new and helps in the development of education in terms of methods, programmes, means and strategies (Abu Al-Wafa, 2011).

This is what Al-Abdulaziz, Al-Qudah, Badran (2016) indicated that the importance of the teacher in this era is due to the explosions and technological revolutions. The teacher is not only a transmitter of knowledge, he is the facilitator and facilitator to push students to discover facts in correct scientific ways. Positive and constructive.

The teacher faces a number of problems that require him to deal with them in the teaching profession.

Problems are defined as "obstacles facing the teacher and hindering him from carrying out his educational role as required of him" (Al-Thibani, 2017, p. 81).

Al-Sharari (2011) refers to a number of problems facing the teacher, namely:

Problems related to school administration, as school administration patterns vary according to the principal's personality and his dealings with the teacher.

Problems with parents. Parents communicate with the teacher, either facilitating the learning process or hindering it through miscommunication between the teacher and parents regarding the request. Parents have a role in the educational process, and their neglect of this role causes tension problems for the teacher.

-Problems related to tasks, the teacher has multiple roles and the tasks assigned to him require effort. The more tasks and activities required of the teacher, the more impact on the educational process and cause problems for the teacher in achieving the goal.

Problems related to training and development, which are one of the important requirements for development and progress in education. The teacher must enroll in courses and programs that help in developing the wheel of education, but sometimes the time and requirements of the courses constitute a burden on the teacher, and whether they are effective or boring.

-Problems related to the student, represented in the increasing of the number of students in the classroom, and consequently, the increase in individual differences and the difference in their characteristics, and the teacher's attempt to deal with them according to their characteristics increases the teacher's conflict.

Therefore, the teacher must have effective characteristics. Muhammad (2020) mentioned some of these characteristics, which are:

Personal traits: the teacher is pots for students and a role model. Among his personal characteristics are emotional balance - justice - endurance - responsibility - humility - honesty - cheerfulness.

Professional and ethical behavior: commitment to the ethical values of the teaching profession, commitment to school laws and regulations, participation in educational, scientific and cultural activities inside and outside the school.

Professional growth of the teacher: through the teacher's participation and enrollment in courses, programs and workshops that advance the educational process.

7. RAMP Initiative:

It is one of the projects embraced by the Ministry of Education in Jordan (Read with perception and settle with comprehension). The Ministry has been executing the program to enact and foster perusing, composing and math abilities for the lower fundamental stage. The educators of the lower essential stage have demonstrated the viability of this program in fostering the expertise of perusing, composing and math. (Freihat, Khreisha 2020).

The drive means to work on the turn of events and advancement of understanding cognizance and math with comprehension. It is a drive embraced by the Jordanian Ministry of Education .

It came to create and foster the essential abilities of the lower fundamental stage, as it changes the perusing interaction from simple perusing to retaining perusing and not simply remembering hard of hearing. It additionally helps in creating numerical abilities for understudies in the lower essential stages, as number juggling is one of the activities that the educator faces trouble in instructing. With the understudies. (2018). The term smash is a contraction of EARLY GRADE READING AND MATHEMATICS PROJECT .

It is the "Perusing and Arithmetic Initiative for the Early Grades" (Ramp Program Guide - Publications of the Ministry of Education, 2017).

Al-Harbi (2019) p. 111 indicates, "Achieving the main objective of the Reading and Arithmetic initiative for the first grades is to enable 55% of all students in the early grades in public schools to read by understanding and solving problems with understanding".

8. Past Studies:

Hamadneh (2017) led an examination pointed toward recognizing the components influencing the accomplishment of the perusing and number juggling drive according to the perspective of instructors and chiefs of fundamental schools in the Bani Kenana District. She dispersed (150) polls to instructors of the lower fundamental stage, with a pace of (half) of the local area who work in the Directorate of Education of the Bani Kinana Brigade, and recovered (101) from them, and after the surveys were returned, it was discovered that there were (12) surveys that were not legitimate for investigation. The quantity of legitimate surveys for measurable investigation was (89), including (29%) of the examination populace, and (40) polls were appropriated to the chiefs of these schools, addressing (58%) of the local area. After the surveys were returned, it was discovered that there are (10) Questionnaires are not substantial for examination. In this way, the quantity of directors in the example was (30), with a pace of (44%), and subsequent to leading the factual investigation, it was tracked down that the request for the elements influencing the accomplishment of the perusing and number-crunching drive as indicated by the assessments of educators, instructors and administrators in the fundamental schools of the Bani Kanana unit It came as follows: stirring inspiration to learn, positive association with understudies, utilizing instructive guides, enhancing boosts and improvements, exercises and targets of the drive, and it was discovered that there was no distinction in the assessments of the examination test individuals about the elements influencing the achievement of the perusing and number-crunching drive as per character factors. (sexual orientation, experience) .

The investigation of Tim, Gabein, Saad, Hamam, and Al-Dalou (2018) intended to distinguish the issues confronting homeroom educators in applying the new Palestinian educational program in government schools in Gaza governorates according to the perspective of the study hall instructors themselves in the light of certain factors, just as uncovering whether there are critical contrasts Statistical importance in the study hall educators' reactions about the issues they face are credited to the accompanying factors: (sex, long periods of involvement, instructive capability, grade). The scientists utilized the enlightening insightful technique to portray the marvel. The investigation test comprised of each of the (180) male and female homeroom educators in government funded schools in the 2017-2018 semester. The specialists arranged a poll for this reason that included (65) issues confronting the class instructors. The investigation found that there are no contrasts among male and female instructors because of sex, long stretches of involvement, grade, and instructive capability.

The study of Khasawneh and Al-Jarrah (2019) aimed to know the problems faced by the teachers of the first three grades of the basic stage in light of the curriculum modification in Irbid Governorate. Do these problems differ according to experience and qualifications? The study sample consisted of a random sample of female

teachers of the first three grades from the first Irbid district, and their number was 200 teachers who hold a master's degree, a bachelor's degree, and an intermediate diploma out of 500 teachers. The two researchers used the construction of a questionnaire consisting of 3 fields. After analyzing the results, it was found that there is an effect of the studied fields on the problems faced by the parameters. The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level attributed to each of the educational qualifications and experience on the problems of the parameters.

Al-Halabi's examination (2015) expected to distinguish the issues looked by educators of the lower fundamental stage in showing English in the schools of Nablus District and as per the factors (sexual orientation, scholastic capability, college of graduation, long stretches of involvement, number of instructional classes, and area of the school). The analyst utilized the enlightening scientific technique, and the specialist fabricated the examination apparatus (the poll, and the investigation test comprised of 116)). The specialist utilized the social measurable bundle spss program. The consequences of the investigation showed that the request for the fields of study came in plummeting request, and the absolute degree accompanied a normal rating.

Al-Harbi's study (2014) also aimed to identify the problems that teachers face in teaching mathematics in the primary grades of the primary school in Riyadh. The descriptive approach was followed in the study and a questionnaire was used, which consisted of 5 axes, and the sample consisted of (113) 102 Mathematics teacher for the primary stage and 11 educational supervisors for mathematics. The results of the study showed that there are problems facing teachers in teaching mathematics.

The MAYARU 2015 investigation zeroed in on the difficulties confronting public elementary teachers in their instructive calling in Tanzania. Mbugoi District, Geeta District The examination plans to explore the reasons for difficulties looked by elementary teachers in their educating calling .

Also, examining the reasonable difficulties that educators face in their showing life and what they mean for the instruction of grade school understudies. Additionally, information on instruction systems, specialists used to work on working conditions in elementary school and educators and to accomplish quality training for grade school students in Mbugui locale .

The investigation utilized a subjective plan. Meetings, conversations and narrative surveys were utilized as a technique for information assortment. The outcomes showed that powerless National Health Insurance (NHIF), helpless administration advancement among instructors, delays in installment of unfulfilled obligations and frail strategy motivating forces and remittances were the fundamental driver of difficulties influencing educators' workplace in Mbugoi region. Additionally, the outcomes showed that instructors' low compensations blocked their capacity to meet fundamental life needs, for example, food and lease installments. The present circumstance influenced educators and did other little activities that influenced their consideration towards getting ready for exercises.

Gündoğmuş Gündoğmus (2018) directed an investigation pointed toward recognizing the challenges that educators looked during the time spent starting perusing and composing guidelines and realizing their answer offers to dispose of these troubles. The investigation bunch comprises of 51 grade teachers who were chosen through the standard example as a kind of intentional examining. The subjective strategy for research was utilized. The meetings were semi-organized with instructors posing them three inquiries. Conclusions were taken recorded as a hard copy to recognize the challenges they experienced during the time spent essential proficiency instruction, and extensively their perspectives were investigated on how these troubles may be and what their answer was. The information acquired from these meetings were dissected by the substance examination strategy .

The outcomes showed that out of 51 essential instructors, 37 were cheerful and 14 were miserable; The hardships they depicted about the interaction included parental impassion, understudies not perusing, showing italic penmanship, absence of expert experience, and non-attendance and absence of interest with respect to the understudies.

9. Methodology:

The descriptive approach was used, which is through which the phenomenon under study can be described, its data analyzed, and the relationships between its components explained.

10. Research community and sample:

The investigation populace comprised of the multitude of female instructors of the lower fundamental stage in state funded schools that carry out the RAM program in the Directorate of Education - Central Badia, and their number was (340) during the primary semester of the scholastic year (2018/2019), as indicated by the Directorate's insights. The two specialists picked an expected arbitrary example of the educators of the lower essential stage in the Muwaqar and Giza regions, and their number was (77) teachers.

The sample as follows:

Table (1)
Frequencies and percentages according to the study variable

	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Students No.	21 and below	33	42.9
	22 and above	44	57.1
Qualification	Diploma	25	32.5
	Bachelor and Higher Studies	52	67.5
		77	100.0

10.1 Study Tool:

To achieve the objectives of the current study, a questionnaire was prepared and includes 15 items.

10.2 Validity of the tool:

Construction veracity:

To remove the build legitimacy of the scale, the relationship coefficients of the provision with the absolute score of the scale were extricated in a review test from outside the examination test that comprised of (20) - , and the connection coefficients of the condition with the all out score of the scale ran between (0.45-0.79), and the accompanying table displays that

table(2)
Correlation coefficients between the paragraph and the total score of the scale

Clause No.	correlation coefficient	Clause No.	correlation coefficient	Clause No.	correlation coefficient
1	.50*	6	.45*	11	.76**
2	.47*	7	.48*	12	.49*
3	.49*	8	.60**	13	.68**
4	.51*	9	.65**	14	.79**
5	.54*	10	.76**	15	.76**

*Statistically significant at the significance level (0.05).

** Statistically significant at the significance level (0.01).

It would be stated that all correlation coefficients were of acceptable and statistically significant degrees, and so far none of these paragraphs were deleted.

10.3 Stability of the Study Instrument:

To guarantee the strength of the investigation device, the test-retest strategy was confirmed by applying the scale, and reapplying it following fourteen days on a gathering outside the examination test comprising of (20), and afterward the Pearson connection coefficient was determined between their appraisals in the multiple times on the off chance that it came to (0.89).

The strength coefficient was additionally determined utilizing the inward consistency strategy as per Cronbach's alpha condition, in the event that it came to (0.84), and these qualities were considered suitable for the reasons for this investigation .

10.4 Study steps and techniques :

Surveying the artistic system and past investigations

Posing an open inquiry to the instructors about the issues they face in carrying out the Ram drive

-Study device is planned .

The examination apparatus was introduced to mediators from college teachers .

The populace and study test were recognized .

- Distributing a poll to the boundaries of the lower essential stage, where the survey comprised of (15) things.

The questionnaire was distributed.

The percentages for each item were found using the educational statistics program (spss).

10.5 Statistical Standard:

The triple Likert scale was adopted to correct the study tools, by giving each of its paragraphs one degree out of its three degrees (a large degree, a medium degree, a small degree), which is represented digitally (3, 2, 1), respectively, and the following scale was adopted for the purposes of analysis Results:

From 1.00-1.66 Low

From 1.67-2.33 medium

From 2.34-3.00 large

And so on

The scale was calculated by using the following equation:

$$\frac{\text{upper end of scale (3) - lower end of scale (1)}}{\text{Number of required categories (3) } 3-1} = 0.66$$

3

After that add the answer (0.66) to the end of each category.

10.6 Study Results and Discussion:

The first question: What are the issues that the educator of the 1st three grades face while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and number juggling?

To address this inquiry, the number juggling midpoints and standard deviations of the issues confronting the 1st three grades boundary while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and math were extricated, and the table beneath displays this.

Table (3)

Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the paragraphs related to the problems facing the first three grades parameter when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic averages

Rank	No.	Clauses	SMA	Standard Deviation	Level
1	15	The difficulty of applying the program with the category of learning difficulties	1.86	.720	average
2	4	There are many students in the classroom	1.82	.790	average
3	11	Non-sequencing in the application of the program between classes	1.82	.739	average
4	3	Lack of time, skills need time to apply	1.81	.762	average
5	9	Not taking into account individual differences	1.78	.661	average
6	10	Poor cooperation by parents in implementing the program	1.77	.724	average
7	8	Overlapping training courses with the Ram program	1.71	.666	average
8	14	Inadequate training courses for teachers	1.71	.758	average
9	13	Many supervisory visits by officials	1.70	.727	average
10	12	The program needs a diversity of teaching aids	1.69	.765	average
11	5	Lack of illustrative materials	1.62	.650	low
12	6	Difficulty applying some skills	1.62	.689	low
13	7	Inappropriate classroom environment	1.60	.712	low
14	2	It takes a lot of effort	1.48	.620	low
15	1	The activities and worksheets accompanying the curriculum are many	1.34	.576	low
		Total mark	1.69	.464	average

Table (3) shows that the number-crunching midpoints ran between (1.34-1.86), where passage No. (15) which expresses "the trouble of applying the program with the class of learning challenges" came in any case with a number juggling normal of (1.86), and the two passages No. (4, and 11), which specify "the quantity of understudies is numerous in the homeroom", and "there is no consecutive utilization of the program between classes" in the second spot with a normal of (1.82), while passage No. (1) came as "exercises and worksheets going with the educational program" Many" positioned last, with a mean of (1.34). The math mean of the issues confronting the 1st three grades boundary while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and number juggling in general was (1.69).

The subsequent inquiry: "Are there measurably critical contrasts ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the issues confronting the instructor of the 1st three grades while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and number-crunching because of the variable number of understudies? "

To address this inquiry, the math midpoints and standard deviations of the issues confronting the educator of the 1st three grades were separated while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and number-crunching as per the variable number of understudies, and to show the measurable contrasts between the number-crunching midpoints, a "t" test was utilized, and the tables beneath represent this.

Table (4)

Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and t-test for the effect of the number of students on the problems facing the first three grades teacher when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic

Student No.	No.	SMA	Standard Deviation	Value "T"	Degrees of Freedom	Statistical Significance
21 and below	33	1.53	.390	-2.675	75	.009
22 and above	44	1.81	.483			

Table (4) shows that there are measurably huge contrasts ($\alpha = 0.05$) because of the impact of the quantity of understudies, and the distinctions are supportive of at least 22 .

The third inquiry: "Are there genuinely critical contrasts ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the issues confronting the educator of the 1st three grades while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and math because of the instructive capability variable"?

To address this inquiry, the math midpoints and standard deviations of the issues confronting the educator of the 1st three grades were removed while applying the RAM program for perusing, composing and number-crunching as per the instructive capability variable, and to show the factual contrasts between the number-crunching midpoints, the "t" test was utilized, and the tables underneath represent this.

Table (5)

Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and the "t" test for the effect of academic qualification on the problems facing the first three grades teacher when applying the RAM program for reading, writing and arithmetic

Qualification	No.	SMA	Standard Deviation	Value "T"	Degrees of Freedom	Statistical Significance
Diploma	25	1.84	.575	2.069	75	.042
Bachelor and higher studies	52	1.61	.384			

Table (5) shows that there are statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the effect of the educational qualification, and the differences are in favor of the diploma.

11. Results and Discussion

Through the results of the current study, which showed the existence of problems among the teachers of the basic stage in the application of the RAM program, which came to a medium degree, we find that the following paragraphs came in the highest 3 degrees, namely "the difficulty of applying the program with the category of learning difficulties" "the number of students is many in the classroom", and "No sequence in applying the program between classes" is one of the most common problems that teachers face, although it is a medium degree. We conclude that the number of students increases, the more problems increase in the application of the program, and this is what the second result agreed with, which came in favor of the number of students in it above 22.

By taking a gander at the consequences of the current examination and past investigations, we find that there is an arrangement between the aftereffects of the current examination and the investigation of Al-Halabi (2015) that there are medium-level issues for the female educators. The aftereffects of the current investigation additionally concurred with the investigation of Al-Khasawneh and Al-Jarrah (2019) that there are issues confronting the boundaries of the lower fundamental stage .

The consequences of the current investigation contrasted concerning the presence of genuinely critical contrasts because of the instructive capability variable with the investigation of Khasawneh and Al-Jarrah (2019), the aftereffects of which showed the shortfall of measurably huge contrasts because of the variable of instructive capability, the investigation of Tim et al. (2018) and the investigation of Al-Halabi (2015) .

12. Recommendations:

The researchers recommend conducting more studies that study the problems facing female teachers and methods of dealing and facing problems.

As well as conducting more studies related to the axes of the Ramp program.

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